

A PROTOTYPE MACHINE FOR THE MANUFACTURE OF FILAMENT-WOUND THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a machine designed to produce filament-wound structures of varying shapes. The use of thermoplastic matrices requires a heating device that follows the actual winding trajectory thus the machine should have at least 7 degrees of freedom ; 3 for the heater path and 4 for the normal winding process. Fully integrated software generates data for the programming of machine operation as well as process simulation. The software version presented covers general axis-symmetrical shapes.

Keys words : Filament winding, thermoplastic prepregs feed-eye, axis-symmetrical structures, fibre-path geodesic trajectory.

INTRODUCTION

The advantages of the filament winding process, based on thermosetting resins, for the manufacture of composite vessels are well-known [1]. These include virtually no limitation as to size, low cost through fast and accurate fibre lay-down, high quality due to uniform fibre placement, low void content and high materials strength through the efficient use of continuous fibres. As a result this technique is widely used for a variety of manufactured goods such as pipes, pressure vessels, storage tanks, missile cases, smoke stacks, etc ... [2], [3]

However, the use of fibre reinforced thermoplastics in filament winding is not common inspite of the potential advantages. For instance, cycle times could be reduced since no curing of the matrix would be necessary and the inherent chemical resistance of most thermoplastics could be of immediate use in the chemical processing industry. In addition no special cleaning would be required as opposed to working with liquid resins and the whole of the impregnation apparatus could be eliminated.

The aim of this study is to define and develop a suitable machine for working with thermoplastic prepregs equipped with an adequate heat source. It is based on the extension of an existing software package produced for simple filament winding so that it can orientate and displace the heat source. The work is currently in progress at ISAT Nevers.

MACHINE DESIGN

To make-up a composite structure from thermoplastic prepregs (generally in ribbon form) it is necessary to heat them sufficiently so as to create a weld, i.e. go from the solid to the liquid state then back again. This allows ribbons to be joined when side-by-side (with slight overlapping) or in layers; The choice is between heating the whole, or a large part of the final

structure, by a static device such as a radiant panel or a stream of hot air or by using an intense beam of energy exactly where it is needed. The first option was abandoned as being wasteful of energy and potentially difficult to control even on small structures and would not allow for scaling-up to structures of several meters in length. It was decided to develop the machine initially for use with an Infra-Red (IR) beam to be directed at all times towards the point of contact (or deposit) between ribbon and mandrel. This choice meant that another possible source of concentrated energy such as a sonotrode, could be substituted since the operating conditions would be comparable. The IR source has to follow the deposit point while remaining at a preset distance from the mandrel and ideally orthogonal to it.

These requirements can be met by two types of design which will be described briefly. Considering the first type using classical winding process control, it was found that, due to the rather complex path taken by the feed-eye for general forms, the deposit point is not always in the same meridian plane. As a result, the heating device, if supported by a cross-beam would need 3 degrees of freedom ; two for displacements in the meridian plane and a third for tilting the plane. This design has already been described in an earlier report which showed that relatively powerful servo-motors were necessary to manipulate the heating device and that it was prone to vibrations [4]. A second alternative design can overcome these shortcomings by providing 2 degrees of freedom within the meridian plane for the heating device, imparting vertical and rotational movement to the feed-eye. This additional motion enables the deposit point to be kept in the meridian plane of the cross-beam support. Thus the motion of the feed-eye involves less inertial effect than tilting of the cross-beam. This design requires 8 degrees of freedom inclusive of the feed-eye notion. A schema of the final design is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic layout of winding machine with heating device in vertical displacement mode

- Key : 1 Micro-computer
 2 Numerical control system (CYBER 3700)
 3 Machine

$M(Xo)$ determines the longitudinal (or axial) movement of the feed-eye

$M(Yo)$ determines the transversal movement of the feed-eye

$M(Zo)$ determines the vertical movement of the feed-eye

$M(Ro)$ determines the rotation of the feed-eye

$M(Xi)$ and $M(Zi)$ determine the longitudinal and vertical movements of the heating head respectively

$M(\beta)$ determines the heating head rotation when the radius changes

and $M(\varnothing)$ determines mandrel rotation

The prototype is basically a 4-axis machine used to test the software during the development stage [5]. The machine was then upgraded to 7 axes to operate the heating head. The final version will have an eighth axis incorporated in order to rotate the heating head around both of its displacement axes so that it can remain normal to the vessel surface during changes in radii.

SYSTEM CONTROL

SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT

The initial software was created to automate a 4-axis filament winding machine for the manufacture of simple cylindrical shapes without end-caps [6]. The displacements incorporated were ; mandrel rotation about a fixed axis, longitudinal and transversal movements of the feed-eye and the rotation of the feed-eye around its transversal displacement axis. The later movement is to ensure that the pre-impregnated fibre ribbon remains flat along the feed-eye width and tangent to the mandrel. Figure 2 shows the feed-eye configuration.

Figure 2. Feed-eye configuration showing

The software package was designed to help small companies engaged in the filament winding of thermosetting resin based composites [7].

The software has evolved to incorporate other process parameters and forms the basis of this report; The first extension was to control a winding machine equipped with a heating device so that glass fibre impregnated with thermoplastics (nylon 6.6) could be used [8]. The second extension, a software version subsequently named PC-Fil 2.0, was to ensure the flat deposit of the fibre ribbon into the mandrel. The innovation in this case was to coincide the ribbon deposit and the heating device movements in the same meridian plane thus eliminating the need to provide for rotation of the heating device around the mandrel axis. Although this configuration has advantages especially with regard to the robustness and power of the machine in order for it to be effective, the control of the feed-eye requires an extra degree of freedom perpendicular to its longitudinal and transversal displacement axes. In addition it is necessary to provide the heating device with 2 degrees of freedom in the deposit plane, one parallel to the mandrel axis and the other along the transverse axis passing through the deposit point. This allows for the heating device to be correctly orientated with respect to the mandrel surface. When winding a vessel of varying radius, then the heating device must be able to rotate around an axis perpendicular to its own displacement plane. See Figure 3.

Figure 3. Apparently simple geometry incorporating end-caps and radius change

ANALYSIS OF MOVEMENTS

Before programming could proceed the expected feed-eye and heating device trajectories had to be evaluated and their equations determined. The positions to be defined at a given moment are : Feed-eye position, F, the contact (or deposit) point where the fibre reaches the mandrel, M, and the heating device position, H. See Figure 4.

Figure 4. Reference system for the heating device H
M is the point of control between ribbon and mandrel

- Key
- γ : deposit meridian ; it is the topmost meridian of the mandrel,
 - \vec{b} : unit vector tangent to γ at point M,
 - ψ : winding angle at point M,
 - R_0 : mandrel radius at point M,
 - λ : constant distance from the feed-eye location F to the deposit point M,
 - γ : deposit meridian
 - $T\psi$: director vector of the fibre at the deposit point,
 - $M(X,O,Z)$ deposit point of the fibre onto mandrel,
 - $F(X_0,Y_0,Z_0)$ feed-eye position,
 - $H(X_h,Y_h,Z_h)$ heating head position

The feed-eye position F is defined by its cartesian coordinates X_0, Y_0, Z_0 such that :

$$X_0 = X - \frac{\lambda \cos \psi}{\sqrt{1 + R_0'^2}} \tag{1}$$

$$Y_0 = \lambda \sin \psi \tag{2}$$

$$Z_0 = R_0 + \frac{\lambda R_0' \cos \psi}{\sqrt{1 + R_0'^2}} \tag{3}$$

The value of ψ is defined by the initial conditions R_{0ini} and ψ_{ini} and the meridian equation

$$R_0 \sin \psi = \text{constant} \tag{4}$$

The angle of rotation of the feed-eye around an axis perpendicular to the vertical plane is β such that :

$$\tan \beta = R'_o \quad (5)$$

The angle of rotation of the feed-eye around an axis perpendicular to the tangent plane to the mandrel at the deposit point M is α such that :

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi}{2} - \psi \quad (6)$$

These two rotational movements are necessary to maintain the fibre ribbon on the centre line of the feed-eye during the winding process. In order to optimise the control parameters of the machine they can be replaced by a single rotation \emptyset around the feed-eye axis of symmetry assigned to remain parallel to the transversal axis (o,y). If \vec{n}_o is the common vector perpendicular to the fibre direction before entering the feed-eye and \vec{T}_ψ the director vector of the fibre ribbon leaving the feed-eye, then it is defined by

$$\vec{n}_o = \vec{j} \wedge \vec{T}_\psi \quad (7)$$

with :

$$\vec{T}_\psi = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \psi \\ \sqrt{1+R_o'^2} \\ -\sin \psi \\ R_o' \cos \psi \\ \sqrt{1+R_o'^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

\vec{n}_o is normal to the plane directed by (\vec{j}, \vec{T}_ψ) and its coordinates are defined by :

$$\vec{n}_o = \begin{pmatrix} R_o' \cos \psi \\ \sqrt{1+R_o'^2} \\ 0 \\ \cos \psi \\ -\sqrt{1+R_o'^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

is a vector in the plane (O,X,Z) directed by (\vec{i}, \vec{j}) Hence the angle \emptyset (Fig. 4) is given by :

$$\phi = \left(\vec{i}, \vec{n}_o \right) \quad \tan \phi = \frac{1}{R'_o} \quad (10)$$

The coordinates of the deposit point M are known, such that :

$$X_M = X \quad (11)$$

$$Y_M = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$Z_M = R_o \quad (13)$$

The position of the heating head H, constrained to remain perpendicular to the mandrel at a constant distance d to the deposit point M, is defined by :

$$X_H = X - \frac{R_o' d}{\sqrt{1 + R_o'^2}} \quad (14)$$

$$Y_H = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$Z_H = R_o + \frac{d}{\sqrt{1 + R_o'^2}} \quad (16)$$

The angle of rotation of the heating device around the perpendicular to the vertical plane is β as defined above.

PROGRAMMING

The software was developed for use with an IBM/PC compatible micro-computer with graphical facilities. The programme enables the following parameters to be monitored and controlled :

- 1- mandrel rotation angle : \emptyset
- 2- longitudinal movement of the feed-eye : X_o
- 3- transversal movement of the feed-eye : Y_o
- 4- vertical movement of the heating device : Z_o
- 5- longitudinal movement of the heating device : X_H
- 6- vertical movement of the heating device : Z_H
- 7- three rotations of the feed-eye : α, β, \emptyset
- 8- two rotations of the heating head : α and β

The general version of software PC-Fil 2.0 is able to control up to 10 axes through only 7 or 8 are usually used. For instance, if the fibre ribbon is narrow then α and β can be suppressed so 7 axes are required . If the ribbons are large then it may be possible to suppress α and β and use the \emptyset -mode only thus requiring 8 axes.

The programme itself is written in Turbo Basic language and generates a file for the process parameters used in either in-plane winding or volume winding depending on the chosen feed-eye movement. The flow chart is presented in Figure 5 and shows the process parameters that have to be introduced. The programme then generates the parameters that will be inter-faced to the numerical control unit and apply to one full cycle or round trip, see Figure 6. In order to achieve a given thickness or coverage of the mandrel then the cycle should be repeated a number of times depending on the ribbon width, the deposit angle ψc , and the large cylinder radius.

Figure 6. Process simulation displayed on graphical facility screen

- Zone (a) : mandrel geometry Zone (b) : displacement of feed-eye in (o,x,y) plane
 Zone (c) : displacement of feed-eye in (o,x,z) plane
 Zone (d) : displacement of heating device in (o,x,z) plane

In the figure the points 1, 2, 3, 4 denote the successive positions of the ribbon deposit point on the mandrel as it is laid down on a geodesic path.

Figure 5. Programme flow chart showing the process parameters that have to be introduced in R.H column

CONCLUSIONS

By modifying existing software, a package has been developed that will enable the filament winding of thermoplastic prepregs to be performed. It is simple to introduce relevant parameters so that it is user-friendly and computation is rapid. The software controls the feed-eye position, mandrel rotation and heater displacement.

The graphical display of the mandrel, feed-eye and heating device movements facilitate operator control of the process. The software has proved its effectiveness in winding various bodies of combined revolution geometries. Future work includes the installation of the heating device on its carrier.

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